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HOW AI IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION CAN HELP TO FOSTER DATA LITERACY AND MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

In the course of the megatrend digitalization, artificial intelligence has recently been receiving a new wave of attention. Within the production environments of the future, engineers and skilled workers will be reliant on information gathered from AI-based assistance systems while developing data-based solutions for complex issues of work. In this respect, integration of recent advances in AI and natural language processing could be of particular importance for engineering education. In respect to the design of engineering curricula, questions arise on how the existing body of knowledge can be linked to the topic of AI and beyond that integrate aspects of e.g. data literacy and motivation. The paper at hand focuses on providing reasons for integrating learning opportunities which deal with AI in engineering education. Therefore, the results of a questionnaire, carried out in the course of a research-oriented seminar, asking prospective technology teachers about their attitudes towards the use of AI in education will be discussed. Furthermore, guidance concerning the design and the integration of peer-to-peer AI workshops, in an interdisciplinary makerspace focusing on engineering education, will be presented. In the course of these learning activities, both future engineers and prospective technology teachers were confronted with reflective tasks in the context of the use of AI-based technology. The synthesis of the observations made, lead to a modular concept proposal to be discussed in this paper. Ultimately, the findings presented here, are perceptions from multiple projects, which will be merged within the framework of a more comprehensive project in the future.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The last few years have seen a renewed interest in artificial intelligence (AI). Here, strategy papers and funding lines focus on the integration of findings from AI research and encourage the development of AI-based applications across all economic sectors [1]. Especially against the background of the recent findings in the AI research fields of Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing (NLP), a technological answer to the qualificational challenges of industry 4.0 by multimodal human-machine interfaces has become increasingly feasible [2]. However, neither the current efforts concerning the integration of data-driven AI methods nor the interdisciplinary research field of AI itself are new [2, 3]. Furthermore, the general importance of data has been distinctive for manufacturing since the origin days of scientific management, and manufacturing already benefited from prior AI methods e.g. statistical process control. Despite this, the new quality and a low-threshold access to AI toolsets for manufacturing have been enabled lately by *Big Data* – i.e. the availability of data and computing power – and the so-called *Algorithm Wave* [4]. The increasing integration efforts on data-driven AI technologies in manufacturing are well documented [4, 5]. In a closer examination, NLP-based cognitive assistant systems should be emphasized as a field of special interest. Here, the recent progress concerning the recurrent neural networks (RNNs) – also see long short-term memory (LSTM) [9] – boosted the expectations about the added value of applications from the field of NLP. The current NLP hype reached its preliminary peak in late 2018 with reports of the human reading comprehension being outstripped by AI applications. And already today, these very same language models establish themselves in communication and expert systems, when start-ups (e.g. huggingface.co) emerge as industrial service providers to create value through data. Eventually, since a large share of the available data in our world is text-based and the importance of technical language in industry practice and engineering education (EE) can be described as a gold standard, a closer look at the field of NLP seems promising to integrate AI in EE [6]. All in all, it can be stated, that these technological phenomena of the digital change will affect working conditions in the future. However, changes in respect to the organization of work, the design of qualification paths, and the offered opportunities for competence development are a necessity for both, skilled workers and aspiring Engineers [7]. Therefore, learning to deal with the impacts of AI-based technology is vital to be able to act professional in the work environments of the future.

The paper at hand takes up the implications of the developments described above and offers a low threshold concept for integrating relevant AI topics in EE. Therefore, the data curation is based on a desk research, the students' and the tutors' feedback, and observations recorded during AI workshops in a makerspace environment. Against this background, research questions to be addressed in the paper at hand are:

- (1) Which learning activities foster competences associated with the topic of AI and the development of meta-cognitive competences for data literacy and motivation?
- (2) What are potential points of reference to integrate AI into the curriculum of EE?

2 OUTLINE OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT LINES

The previously outlined aspects indicate that questions related to the design and the application-oriented integration of AI-based technologies are relevant for the further development of EE. This section describes the lines of development in AI, provides a work definition and underlines the importance of NLP for AI-based assistance in EE.

2.1 From electronic therapist to cognitive assistance

The transfer of human decision making to technical objects and its delimitation from human intelligence had already involved a variety of disciplines for some time when the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence (DSRPAI) in 1956 generated the starting point for the interdisciplinary field of AI research [8]. Up to the 1970s, the field of AI research was characterized by heuristic algorithms that were implemented manually using symbol-based programming languages. Following this period of rule-based AI, logic-oriented and functional programming languages became more and more accepted and the rise of statistic-based AI began, a time coined by the so-called expert systems [4]. At the beginning of the 1990s, the AI hype came to an end anew, once again due to overdrawn expectations towards these knowledge-based systems. The research work carried on at that time was a key enabler for many AI applications established today (e.g.: "history of backpropagation" in [9]). In a third phase learning systems based on deep learning algorithms dominated the field. In the upcoming fourth phase it is expected that cognitive systems will recognise the necessary contextual adaptations and use learning to update the knowledge base autonomously. The outlined developments of AI are shown schematically in figure 1.

Figure 1: Previous phases of AI development [10]

As elaborated in the previous descriptions, the field of AI is in a state of evolution. Furthermore, the underlying notion of intelligence is, as an inherent part of human dispositions and despite the recent neuroscientific efforts, still not comprehensively defined at this point. Based on the perspectives discussed in [5], and in the course of the present article, AI is defined as a field of computer science, describing the efforts to reconstruct e.g. human decision making and problem-solving with the assistance of AI-based technologies (e.g. RNNs), to overcome human limitations (in regards to the amount and the complexity of data) and thereby support mankind cognitively.

Prominent areas of AI application are quality control, optimized resource management, robotics, predictive analytics, knowledge management, intelligent sensor technology, intelligent automation, autonomous driving \ flying, and intelligent assistance systems. A commonly used structure for the areas of AI-related research is listed below[9]:

- Rational approaches (measurable or objective criteria exist):
 - Rules of complex processes \ action planning and optimization (e.g.: Route planning, self-orientation, navigation etc.)
 - Application of learning procedures \ machine learning (e.g.: statistical models, un-\ supervised \ reinforcement learning)
 - Recognition of image and image sequences via computer vision (e.g.: in the course of object, environment or affect recognition etc.)
- Behaviour-oriented approaches (unpredictability of requirements):
 - Representation of knowledge networks via semantic technologies (e.g.: Linked Open Data, Ontologies etc.)
 - Understanding natural language via natural language processing (e.g.: translations, question-answer systems, text-to-speech etc.)
 - Cognitive modelling (e.g.: simulation of emotion, decision making etc)
- Neuromorphic computing: i.e. hardware architectures imitating the human brain

In respect to the technology-related backgrounds presented, it may be stated that, both with regard to the basic statistical methodological knowledge and with regard to the relevance of current fields of application, AI proves to be a relevant topic for EE.

2.2 About the relevance of NLP-based assistance systems in EE

In a more detailed analysis of the relevant fields for the use of AI-based technologies the integration of cognitive assistance systems offers a promising perspective for EE [4, 5]. Here, NLP, in the sense of applied engineering and as a subfield of AI, combines findings from computer science, computational linguistics, and machine learning, provides the key bridge technology to enable human-machine collaboration. NLP describes the design of AI-based technology that enables machines to be able to read, process, generate and understand human languages [11]. includes language understanding and generation (NLP = NLU + NLG). Moreover, it is considered to be one of the most important application areas of artificial intelligence. It offers, in addition to low-threshold and practical access to the topic of language as a data source, several applications with references to the everyday reality of learners [12]. The broad field of applications, e.g. assistance and recommender systems, language translation, information retrieval and extraction, text analytics, predictive text, voice recognition, or the use of search engines underlines the comprehensive opportunities for competence development. For a more in-depth study of NLP, please refer to the works of [13, 14]. Furthermore, the Workshop Building Educational Applications (BEA) as the leading venue for NLP innovation in the context of educational applications organized by the Special Interest Group in Educational Applications (SIGEDU) should be noted [15]. Finally, e.g. Bhaduri validated the growing relevance of machine learning and NLP techniques especially for instruction and research context in the field of EE [6].

3 METHODOLOGY

The paper at hand is structured following the logic of triangulation, including a literature review, the discussion of the students' learner traces, and additional indications from formative feedback. Focusing the design of innovative learning venues, challenges such as the growing complexity [7], the individualisation of learning paths, and the documentation of digital traces, mapping these processes and the learning community are highly relevant to EE [17]. Recommendations, towards a modular course design presented here, are based on a design-based research approach (DBR), whereby this publication can be seen as a first test to the underlying hypothesis [16]. While these basic conditions are also taken up at the political programme level and may be understood as a claim rather than a challenge with concern to the design of teaching and learning, conditions for success or even recommendations for implementation are still lacking in context with the integration of AI in engineering education [18]. For a more comprehensive examination concerning the recent course of dealing with the integration of AI technology in education, please refer e.g. to the publication of Zawacki-Richter et al. [19].

The survey, which is presented in the following, used a questionnaire developed with prospective technology teachers in a course on research-orientation. The overall course design is also subject to a DBR approach focusing innovations of EE in context with the scholarship of teaching and learning, i.e. dealing with questions concerning autonomy, motivation and the impact of AI-based assistant systems [20]. The questionnaire was conducted as pen and paper format addressing multiple groups of students in teacher training in winter term 2019 / 2020. The students' hypothesis assumed a correlation between the assessment of AI technology and the attitude towards the use of AI in education (H1). Therefore, a first self-assessment on AI asked at which point the respondent would classify the use of a technology as AI in education. The participants were asked to mark their views with a cross at any position, while on the far-left side the scale starts with "Smartboards", and is limited with "Learning software with independent network features" on the right end (see fig. 2 – the scaling is intended to help to interpret the results and does not correspond to the original figure given in the course of the questionnaire). Also, data about the personal opinion on the use of AI in education has been collected by asking for a level of agreement concerning 10 statements on AI (scale: does agree = 4, does rather agree = 3, does rather not agree = 2, does not disagree = 1). Furthermore, the learners decided to differentiate between age and gender in order to be able to set priorities in the subsequent reflection reports, which represent their study assessment.

As mentioned above, the overall research design includes the collection of demands, attitudes and prior knowledge in the context of AI (in education) on the one hand and an iterative implementation and evaluation of different learning opportunities on the other hand. The data from the formative evaluation, the queries of prior knowledge, and the students' and the tutors' feedback regarding peer-to-peer workshops on AI were collected in two consecutive semesters (summer term 2019 and winter term 2019 / 2020) in a makerspace environment focusing on engineering education [21].

4 RESULTS: LEARNERS' REFLECTIONS ON THE USE OF AI

The following section introduces results of a questionnaire, the findings concerning the implementation of peer-to-peer workshops on AI and outlines the preliminary findings.

4.1 A students' survey asking their fellow students about the relevance of AI

All in all, 96 persons participated the questionnaire. After data cleansing data reports on a total of 95 surveys. 55 are female (% 23.4 years), 39 are male (% 24.1 years). 75 are enrolled in a MINT subject, 56 are in a Bachelors', and 37 in a Masters' degree.

Figure 2 illustrates the self-assessment item about technology use in education, which differs from the depiction in the survey i.e. with regard to the here inserted numbering. Findings show a mean value of 11.3 for women, which represents "speech or text recognition" and a slightly higher mean value for men (12.6), which represents "smart translation systems". Concerning the breakdown of answers, please refer to figure 3.

Figure 2: Answer scale self-assessment "Which technology level corresponds to AI in education?"

Figure 3: Results of the self-assessment "What does AI in education mean to you?"

Table 1 presents the results concerning the items asking for the attitude towards AI. The largest differences in the average response to the statements are found at item C6 (AI-based applications could especially support learners with special educational needs) with 0.56 points and C8 (I am familiar with the topic of AI) with 0.46 points.

While women tend to agree more with the statement C6, it is the men in C8 who claim to be familiar with the topic. All in all, the answers underline that AI in teaching is not only a general gain C1 (The use of AI is a benefit for the learners) but can also be a relief for the teachers C4 (AI-based applications could ease my teaching load in the future). Currently, the participants do not feel well-prepared C3 (I feel that my studies have prepared me for working with AI-based technology), state that C8 (In the next 5 years, the topic of AI will become increasingly important in teaching), and agree with the statement that the topic is gaining in importance C7 (I'm familiar with AI). On the other hand, they state that they are prepared to deal with the topic C10 (I am ready to deal with the topic AI). In addition, there is a high correlation between C5 (I think it makes sense to use AI in teaching) and C6 (In the next 5 years, the topic of AI will become increasingly important in teaching.). Regarding C9 (I consider the use of AI in teaching to be problematic) it can be said, that, like C2 (I see additional work coming my way using AI in teaching) the participants of the peer-to-peer survey slightly agree.

Table 1. Attitude towards AI

Criteria	Age & Attitudes	Gender & Attitudes	General Approval Ratings	
	Pearson's r p-value	Pearson's r p-value	M SD	Female Male
C1 benefit	- 0.215 0.981	- 0.233 0.988	2.94 0.700	3.07 2.74
C2 work	0.093 0.187	0.215 0.019	2.76 0.859	2.60 2.97
C3 able	- 0.112 0.859	0.106 0.155	1.64 0.757	1.58 1.74
C4 relief	- 0.065 0.733	0.028 0.393	2.84 0.624	2.87 2.85
C5 use	- 0.200 0.973	- 0.181 0.960	2.87 0.718	2.98 2.72
C6 special	- 0.093 0.811	- 0.354 1.000	3.07 0.782	3.30 2.74
C7 weight	- 0.153 0.930	0.079 0.226	3.21 0.742	3.16 3.28
C8 familiar	0.099 0.171	0.269 0.004	1.88 0.849	1.69 2.15
C9 change	- 0.239 0.989	- 0.066 0.736	2.66 0.849	2.30 2.41
C10 deal	- 0.046 0.670	0.096 0.178	3.18 0.753	3.11 3.26

The initial assumption that there are correlations between the classification of AI and the attitude towards using AI in education (H1) can be confirmed by the questionnaire. All in all, students for whom the threshold of AI is higher are more negative towards the use of AI in education (C1; $r = -.236, p < .05$) In particular, they feel less comfortable through prepared the course for work with AI-based technologies (C3; $r = -.258, p < .05$) see less of a workload relief in AI systems (C4; $r = -.296, p < .01$) and appreciate the importance than students with lower acceptance of AI (C7; $r = -.210, p < .05$).

4.2 Design and integration of peer-to-peer workshops on AI

In the course of the design and implementation of peer-to-peer workshops addressing AI-related competences, additional learners' reflections were collected. All in all, in the last two semesters 110 students from engineering faculty and technology teaching participated workshops on topics like IoT (Raspberry, Arduino), 3D-Printing, Virtual Reality, and the basics of AI \ NLP. Further publications are planned in this regard [21].

A key observation regarding the assessment of prior knowledge is, that participants had relevant prior knowledge of mathematics and statistics, which has so far not been effectively linked to the AI topics, methods or applications. Hands-on experiences, like here, are taken in addition to the general workload of the semester. Regarding the research questions established in section one, the analysed learners' and tutors' feedback revealed that (1) research-oriented activities including questions on the topic of AI can be applied by students on a high-quality level, (2) prior statistical knowledge is currently not connected with AI topics. Here, AI- or, to be more specific, NLP-based assistant systems offer multiple points of reference to integrate hands-on activities.

5 AN NLP-BASED APPROACH TO INTEGRATE AI METHODOLOGY IN EE

The following section provides answers for the previously stated research questions based on the generated results and therefore outlines a first modular approach to the integration of AI methods in the context of EE by designing a tailored learning activity in the context of an implementation and reflection of a cognitive assistance system.

5.1 How can AI help to foster data literacy?

Data Literacy (DL) refers to the ability to critically analyse and interpret data, to apply procedures and methods in the context with the collection, management, evaluation and application of data in order to extract knowledge and value from data sources [22]. The overall importance of DL became more and more observable since the curricular integration of learning opportunities focused on the application of the data-rich basic technologies in context with competences for industry 4.0, e.g. Internet of Things. [23]. Due to a significant overlap of competences, DL is considered to be one of several critical literacies, mind and skillsets, which in some instances build upon each other. This refers to e.g. information and science data information, statistical, computational, machine learning, visitational and also ethical or critical literacy frameworks. Today, DL can be described as a focus area of competence development, also due to the further increasing relevance of data science [24]. While DL is an enabler to transform information into actionable knowledge and become able to act, there is a tremendous requirement for learning opportunities that offer low threshold scenarios for an application of relevant technologies, like cognitive assistant systems. Furthermore, these settings should include an accompanying reflection of the impact on the before mentioned concepts to gain metacognitive competencies within problem-oriented, project-based and interdisciplinary learning venues [25]. In order to initiate these reflection processes, in the sense of individualized learning and the assessment of the current level of competence acquisition, assistance systems based on AI technology provide an excellent vehicle to support both on part of the teachers and the learners.

5.2 How can AI help to foster motivation?

The goal-setting theory offers important insights into how to promote student motivation. [26] The four main moderators are ability, task complexity, performance feedback, and goal commitment. AI-based technology can help to address each of these points and thus promote the motivation of students. Ability means that learners

must have the necessary knowledge to solve a task. It is difficult for teachers to find out whether all their students have the necessary skills to complete a task, especially if there are a large number of students. An AI-based assistance system that monitors and evaluates the competence development of learners over a longer period of time can ensure that learners in the game only get tasks that they are able to solve at all. Furthermore, it is crucial that a task is not only generally solvable, but also that the learners are neither under- nor overchallenged. From a didactic point of view, it is often useful to give the learners a lot of freedom in their own development of new knowledge and to promote self-learning processes. Some students, however, quickly feel overtaxed by less structured learning processes, while learners may feel undertaxed in overly structured learning processes. It is difficult for teachers to know and take into account individual abilities. By observing the working methods (and possibly biometric data) an AI-based assistance system is able to consider the right degree of complexity for each student. Continuous feedback also has a positive effect on the motivation of students in learning processes: The better students know whether they are on the right track, the better they can adapt their strategy and achieve motivating success. An AI-based assistance system can analyze individual work steps of the learners and predict expected work steps and provide timely support before learners become demotivated by failure. Goal commitment is an aspect that is too often neglected in higher education teaching. In order to develop motivation, a goal that learners have set for themselves is necessary. Teachers set their focus on their learning outcomes, but usually not on the individual goals of their students, such as passing an exam, getting a good grade, obtaining a degree or being among the better students and thus possibly receiving further rewards. These are usually medium to long-term goals. But the more students are aware of their own and short-term goals, the more motivated they are to put work into achieving them. This is too much effort for teachers, but an AI system can help to get a picture of the overall goals of individual learners and help them to break down these goals into short-term goals and relate them to current tasks. All in all, an AI-based assistance system is thus more efficient in addressing the four main factors of the goal setting theory in higher education teaching and actively supporting students in promoting their motivation.

5.3 A Tutor for Artificial Intelligence supported Learning in Engineering

A Tutor for **Artificial Intelligence supported Learning in Engineering** or *TAILing* describes an approach of the curricular integration of AI-related topics, while focusing on meta-cognitive competences in the context of data literacy and motivation (fig. 4). This Approach is built upon the idea of self-directed and AI-assisted learning, where the implementation of an AI-/NLP-based assistant serves as a vehicle for application. Here, learning activities in interdisciplinary teams to (co-) design such a tool offers vast possibilities of reflectional tasks for the learners, can be used as a mediator between learners' attitudes towards the use of AI, their peers and the instructors and serve as an accompanying consultant for the teachers. In using several NLP-related open-source repositories, the learners can create an AI assistant system that monitors and evaluates individual competence development throughout the course on a basic level.

They build their personal learning assistant on their own and by doing so, they reflect on the compatibility of data interfaces, data sources, questions of ethics, and more.

Figure 4: Outline of the pillars and the foundation of TAILing

The course design is planned as an interactive (h5p), supervised and asynchronous online course, which ties into the learners prior knowledge specific to their curriculum and thus enables the development of basic competences in the context of AI and the aforementioned meta-cognitive competences regarding data literacy and motivation. The course is interlocked with interdisciplinary workshops in a Makerspace, which promotes a co-creative and project-oriented application of AI-related basics. Following the successful participation in the "AI basics" course (60 hours | 2 ECTS), the in-depth blended learning course "Decision-making with AI-based information" will be taken, which transfers findings of NLP to implement an AI tutor for EE (90 hours | 3 ECTS).

6 SUMMARY

So far, the analysis of the potential of AI-based assistance systems in higher education teaching has focused on students' activities. This makes sense in some respects, but also implies an understanding that teachers could potentially become superfluous in such scenarios. In fact, the question of what role teachers will play in increasingly AI-supported teaching is becoming more important, given that they will be relieved of the essential tasks of student support. Will they remain important in supporting learning processes or in evaluating learning outcomes? Or is their role limited to curricular aspects, the definition of learning goals and the development of learning modules? Will they (have to) work together with an AI system in order to control the didactically meaningful support of learners? What is the interaction between teachers and the AI-based systems like? Will teachers and engineers in future need an AI assistance to help them design their AI assisted teaching? Research on and development of AI-supported learning processes should take these issues even more into account. In addition, key questions regarding the impact of the increasing dependency on AI-based information systems, concerning data literacy and motivational aspects, need a profound answer to meet the requirements of future AI-influenced venues of work.

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